

“Morphological Differences are Predicted by Geographic Location for Maastrichtian *Gunnarites* from the James Ross Basin, Antarctica”

SUPPLEMENT TEXT

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Naze Scaling Relationships

To determine the best-supported threshold value (WH) for each Naze Threshold Model, we followed the methodology outlined by Mohr et al. (2024): the range of possible threshold values was selected for each response variable such that at least 10 data points were present below the lowest evaluated threshold position and at least 10 data points were present above the highest evaluated threshold position. The best-supported threshold value and associated 95% confidence interval was determined using Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)-based model selection (Burnham and Anderson 2002) and the method of Ulm and Cox (1989).

Results of the LMMs characterizing scaling relationships for specimens from The Naze (Naze Single-Slope Models and Naze Threshold Models) are shown in Supplementary Tables 3–4, which also include the results of likelihood ratio tests comparing the performance of both models for each response variable (see main text section “Scaling Relationships for Naze Specimens”). The scaling relationship described by the best-performing model for each response variable is shown in Supplementary Figures 1–2.

Elevation Effects for Naze Specimens

Although most specimens in our dataset do not have associated high-resolution stratigraphic information, 22 specimens collected from The Naze have relative elevation information from direct on-site measurements. Fossil specimens were common on the surface, but the stratigraphy was poorly exposed in the collection area and not logged in detail due to field time constraints, though locally the strata dip shallowly (~10° SW). Specimens are thus placed in relative stratigraphic position suitable for the following analysis, but should not be considered absolute stratigraphic positions relative to known sections on The Naze. To evaluate whether any detectable stratigraphic variation in morphology occurs within this sample of specimens, we fit an LMM for each response variable, incorporating “elevation” (in meters) as an additional continuous explanatory variable, and compared it to an otherwise identical model excluding elevation information. None of the models incorporating elevation information outperformed models without

this information (in likelihood ratio tests), and the coefficient on the elevation variable was not found to be significant for any of the models (see Supplementary Tables 1–2); taken together, this indicates that, for our limited dataset of 22 specimens with detailed stratigraphic information, no detectable differences in morphology resulting from different stratigraphic position were observed.

Correlations Between Variables

Correlations between morphological variables were evaluated with Spearman's rank correlation using R package Hmisc (Harrell 2023). Results were plotted using R package corrplot (Wei and Simko 2021; see Supplementary Fig. 3). Repeated measurements from within an individual specimen are not independent, so only measurements from one ontogenetic position per individual were included in the calculation of Spearman's rank correlations. For each specimen, the ontogenetic position with the fewest missing observations of morphometric variables was selected, and the position representing the latest ontogeny was selected as a tiebreaker when needed.

Supplementary Tables

		WWI		WRER		Z		Ribsins	
Naze Single-Slope Model	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>
	Intercept	0.121 [0.073, 0.166]	<0.001	0.126 [0.066, 0.191]	<0.001	-3.840 [-10.434, 2.308]	0.242	1.013 [1.000, 1.024]	<0.001
	Whorl Height (WH)	-0.130 [-0.170, -0.092]	<0.001	0.176 [0.122, 0.230]	<0.001	6.816 [1.182, 12.728]	0.023	-0.000 [-0.011, 0.011]	0.99
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.002	0.799	0.001	0.346	10.822	0.423	0.000	0.327
	Residual	0.001		0.001		14.763		0.000	
Variance Explained by the Model	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	
	0.291	0.858	0.570	0.719	0.075	0.466	0	0.327	
Naze Single-Slope Elevation	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>
	Intercept	0.156 [0.100, 0.211]	<0.001	0.126 [0.066, 0.190]	0.001	-4.364 [-11.545, 2.376]	0.215	1.011 [0.998, 1.024]	<0.001
	Whorl Height (WH)	-0.122 [-0.162, -0.085]	<0.001	0.169 [0.104, 0.230]	<0.001	6.371 [0.335, 12.483]	0.043	-0.002 [-0.014, 0.010]	0.712
	Elevation	-0.002 [-0.005, 0.000]	0.077	0.000 [-0.002, 0.002]	0.642	0.053 [-0.167, 0.285]	0.642	0.000 [-0.000, 0.001]	0.313
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.002	0.777	0.001	0.347	11.364	0.435	0.000	0.337
Residual	0.001		0.001		14.770		0.000		
Variance Explained by the Model	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	R^2_m	R^2_c	
	0.434	0.874	0.566	0.717	0.085	0.483	0.023	0.352	
Sample Size	n		n		n		n		
Specimens	21		20		22		22		
Observations	81		57		96		96		
Model Comparison (LRT)	Model Deviance	LogL <i>P</i>	Model Deviance	LogL <i>P</i>	Model Deviance	LogL <i>P</i>	Model Deviance	LogL <i>P</i>	
Naze Single-Slope Model	-328.46		-215.82		559.74		-631.67		
Naze Single-Slope Elevation Model	-331.99	0.06	-216.15	0.565	559.49	0.618	-632.79	0.289	

Supplementary Table 1. Linear Mixed Model (LMM) results contrasting the results of the Naze Single-Slope Model and the Naze Single-Slope Elevation Model (with “elevation” as an additional continuous explanatory variable; see Supplement Text section “Elevation Effects for Naze Specimens”), for response variables best-fit by the Naze Single-Slope Model (versus the Naze Threshold Model; see Supplementary Tables 3–4). In all models, whorl height (WH) was log-transformed before analysis; response variables representing measures of conch morphology (WWI and WRER) were also log-transformed before analysis (see main text Fig. 3 for variable abbreviations). Repeatability (Rep.) quantifies the proportion of the total variance (after removing the variance explained by the fixed effects) attributed to specimen identity (a unique identifier for each specimen). Marginal R^2 values (R^2_m) report the proportion of variance in the response variable explained by a model’s fixed effects (here, WH) and conditional R^2 values (R^2_c) report the proportion of variation in the response variable explained by both the fixed (WH) and random effects (specimen identity). “Model Comparison” section reports

results of a likelihood ratio test comparing the performance of both LMMs, including deviance for each model and associated p-value (*P*) for the chi-squared statistic. For each variable, the results of the best-performing model are in bold, with green table headings.

		UWI		RUWI		WHER		OR		IR	
Naze Threshold Model	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>
	Intercept	-0.381 [-0.447, -0.314]	<0.001	-0.505 [-0.578, -0.435]	<0.001	-0.142 [-0.316, 0.028]	0.1	15.482 [11.702, 19.018]	<0.001	10.898 [7.838, 14.104]	<0.001
	WH (slope before threshold)	-0.074 [-0.133, -0.019]	0.013	0.079 [-0.003, 0.154]	0.034	0.475 [0.299, 0.654]	<0.001	-9.004 [-12.908, -5.177]	<0.001	-4.321 [-7.633, -1.348]	0.008
	WH (slope after threshold)*	-0.133 [-0.230, -0.035]	0.01	-0.196 [-0.235, -0.157]	<0.001	0.146 [0.020, 0.273]	0.035	8.278 [6.172, 10.384]	<0.001	3.059 [0.822, 5.296]	0.009
	Threshold (mm WH)	21	NA	9	NA	12	NA	11	NA	12	NA
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.002	0.928	0.002	0.797	0.001	0.183	1.589	0.7	0.636	0.498
	Residual	0.000		0.000		0.002		0.679		0.642	
	Variance Explained by the Model	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c
		0.208	0.943	0.285	0.855	0.647	0.711	0.32	0.796	0.119	0.557
Naze Threshold Elevation Model	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>
	Intercept	-0.365 [-0.433, -0.295]	<0.001	-0.491 [-0.570, -0.418]	<0.001	-0.142 [-0.324, 0.032]	0.112	14.971 [11.171, 18.554]	<0.001	10.856 [7.760, 14.043]	<0.001
	WH (slope before threshold)	-0.060 [-0.123, -0.001]	0.055	0.082 [0.004, 0.159]	0.029	0.476 [0.282, 0.667]	<0.001	-9.347 [-13.129, -5.516]	<0.001	-4.507 [-8.037, -1.354]	0.007
	WH (slope after threshold)*	-0.129 [-0.261, 0.004]	0.012	-0.195 [-0.310, -0.079]	<0.001	0.152 [-0.172, 0.477]	0.041	8.066 [1.839, 14.292]	<0.001	3.003 [-2.653, 8.659]	0.012
	Threshold (mm WH)	21	NA	9	NA	12	NA	11	NA	12	NA
	Elevation	-0.002 [-0.004, 0.001]	0.173	-0.001 [-0.003, 0.002]	0.479	-0.000 [-0.003, 0.003]	0.948	0.048 [-0.026, 0.131]	0.255	0.013 [-0.046, 0.074]	0.67
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.002	0.925	0.002	0.801	0.001	0.212	1.553	0.695	0.670	0.510
	Residual	0.000		0.000		0.002		0.680		0.642	
	Variance Explained by the Model	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c
	0.297	0.947	0.316	0.864	0.642	0.718	0.365	0.807	0.122	0.570	
Sample Size	n		n		n		n		n		
Specimens	20		22		20		21		21		
Observations	62		146		59		96		84		
Model Comparison (LRT)	Model Deviance	LogL <i>P</i>	Model Deviance	LogL <i>P</i>	Model Deviance	LogL <i>P</i>	Model Deviance	LogL <i>P</i>	Model Deviance	LogL <i>P</i>	
Naze Threshold Model	-308.42		-629.15		-179.89		282.73		230.93		
Naze Threshold Elevation Model	-310.56	0.144	-629.72	0.45	-179.89	0.992	281.23	0.221	230.71	0.644	

Supplementary Table 2. Linear Mixed Model (LMM) results contrasting the results of the Naze Threshold Model and the Naze Threshold Elevation Model (with “elevation” as an additional continuous explanatory variable; see Supplement Text section “Elevation Effects for Naze Specimens”), for response variables best-fit by the Naze Threshold Model (versus the Naze Single-Slope Model; see Supplementary Tables 3–4). In all models, whorl height (WH) was log-transformed before analysis; response variables representing measures of conch

morphology (UWI, RUWI, and WHER) were also log-transformed before analysis (see main text Fig. 3 for variable abbreviations). Fixed effect coefficients “WH (slope after threshold)*” are not direct outputs of the model, but are calculated using model coefficients. Repeatability (Rep.) quantifies the proportion of the total variance (after removing the variance explained by the fixed effects) attributed to specimen identity (a unique identifier for each specimen). Marginal R² values (R²_m) report the proportion of variance in the response variable explained by a model’s fixed effects (here, WH) and conditional R² values (R²_c) report the proportion of variation in the response variable explained by both the fixed (WH) and random effects (specimen identity). “Model Comparison” section reports results of a likelihood ratio test comparing the performance of both LMMs, including deviance for each model and associated p-value (P) for the chi-squared statistic. For each variable, the results of the best-performing model are in bold, with green table headings.

		WWI		UWI		RUWI		WHER		WRER	
Naze Single-Slope Model	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P
	Intercept	0.126 [0.082, 0.170]	<0.001	-0.391 [-0.432, -0.348]	<0.001	-0.350 [-0.382, -0.322]	<0.001	0.111 [0.045, 0.176]	0.002	0.191 [0.142, 0.240]	<0.001
	Whorl Height (WH)	-0.133 [-0.168, -0.098]	<0.001	-0.076 [-0.109, -0.042]	<0.001	-0.116 [-0.139, -0.090]	<0.001	0.208 [0.156, 0.263]	<0.001	0.119 [0.078, 0.159]	<0.001
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.003	0.761	0.002	0.911	0.002	0.703	0.001	0.348	0.001	0.354
	Residual	0.001		0.000		0.001		0.002		0.001	
Variance Explained by the Model	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	
	0.256	0.822	0.183	0.927	0.273	0.784	0.466	0.652	0.344	0.576	
		WWI		UWI		RUWI		WHER		WRER	
Naze Threshold Model	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P
	Intercept	0.104 [0.025, 0.178]	<0.001	-0.436 [-0.487, -0.384]	<0.001	-0.508 [-0.567, -0.454]	<0.001	-0.018 [-0.147, 0.105]	0.002	0.171 [0.106, 0.231]	<0.001
	WH (slope before threshold)	-0.108 [-0.181, -0.028]	0.005	-0.033 [-0.075, 0.010]	0.128	0.072 [0.014, 0.133]	0.018	0.347 [0.213, 0.478]	<0.001	0.139 [0.085, 0.197]	<0.001
	WH (slope after threshold)*	-0.149 [-0.200, -0.097]	<0.001	-0.150 [-0.210, -0.090]	<0.001	-0.183 [-0.213, -0.153]	<0.001	0.130 [0.051, 0.209]	0.002	0.078 [-0.015, 0.171]	0.105
	Threshold (mm WH)	11 [<6, >30]	NA	21 [7.778, 29.042]	NA	9 [7.922, 9.639]	NA	12 [<7, >35]	NA	19 [<7, >35]	NA
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
Specimen ID	0.003	0.774	0.002	0.932	0.002	0.785	0.001	0.27	0.001	0.334	
Residual	0.001		0.000		0.001		0.002		0.001		
Variance Explained by the Model	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	
	0.250	0.830	0.153	0.942	0.290	0.848	0.498	0.634	0.350	0.567	
		WWI		UWI		RUWI		WHER		WRER	
Sample Size	n		n		n		n		n		
Specimens	42		40		42		40		40		
Observations	149		125		286		118		116		
		WWI		UWI		RUWI		WHER		WRER	
Model Comparison (LRT)	Model Deviance	LogL P	Model Deviance	LogL P	Model Deviance	LogL P	Model Deviance	LogL P	Model Deviance	LogL P	
Naze Single-Slope Model	-538.75		-609.18		-1155.32		-354.21		-415.10		
Naze Threshold Model	-539.25	0.477	-616.28	0.008	-1197.13	<0.001	-359.43	0.022	-416.05	0.329	

Supplementary Table 3. Linear Mixed Model (LMM) results contrasting the results of the single-slope model (“Naze Single-Slope Model”) and threshold model (“Naze Threshold Model”) for specimens from The Naze, and for response variables representing conch morphology (see “Scaling Relationships for Naze Specimens” in the main text; see main text Fig. 3 for variable abbreviations). Response and explanatory variables were log-transformed before analysis. For the Naze Threshold Model, fixed effect coefficient “WH (slope after threshold)*” is not a direct output of the model, but is calculated using model coefficients. Repeatability (Rep.) quantifies the proportion of the total variance (after removing the variance explained by the fixed effects) attributed to specimen identity (a unique identifier for each specimen). Marginal R² values (R²_m) report the proportion of variance in the response variable explained by a model’s fixed effects (here, WH) and conditional R² values (R²_c) report the proportion of variation in the response variable explained by both the fixed (WH) and random effects (specimen identity). “Model Comparison” section reports results of a likelihood ratio test comparing the performance of both LMMs, including deviance for each model and associated p-value (*P*) for the chi-squared statistic. For each variable, the results of the best-performing model are in bold, with green table headings. Confidence intervals for the position of the threshold were not able to be estimated in cases where they exceeded the boundaries of the range of possible threshold values tested (see Supplement Text section “Naze Scaling Relationships” for further detail).

		Z		RibsIn		OR		IR	
Naze Single-Slope Model	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>
	Intercept	-5.826 [-10.558, -0.675]	0.021	1.007 [0.997, 1.016]	<0.001	4.851 [3.388, 6.284]	<0.001	6.835 [5.229, 8.294]	<0.001
	Whorl Height (WH)	8.933 [4.268, 12.997]	<0.001	0.006 [-0.001, 0.015]	0.108	2.855 [1.626, 4.025]	<0.001	0.368 [-0.862, 1.669]	0.565
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	11.151	0.423	0.000	0.232	1.427	0.593	1.344	0.582
	Residual	15.240		0.000		0.979		0.966	
Variance Explained by the Model	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	
	0.130	0.497	0.021	0.248	0.150	0.654	0.003	0.583	
Naze Threshold Model	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>	Est. [95%CI]	<i>P</i>
	Intercept	8.523 [-25.090, 39.466]	0.021	0.992 [0.969, 1.016]	<0.001	15.272 [12.044, 18.309]	<0.001	12.762 [9.918, 15.557]	<0.001
	WH (slope before threshold)	-8.556 [-44.913, 31.710]	0.658	0.023 [-0.002, 0.048]	0.079	-8.281 [-11.412, -5.112]	<0.001	-5.872 [-8.704, -3.011]	<0.001
	WH (slope after threshold)*	9.876 [5.224, 14.528]	<0.001	0.002 [-0.009, 0.012]	0.773	6.772 [5.318, 8.226]	<0.001	3.408 [1.651, 5.165]	<0.001
	Threshold (mm WH)	7 [<7, >33]	NA	10 [<7, >33]	NA	11 [9.880, 11.924]	NA	12 [7.890, 13.758]	NA
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
Specimen ID	11.612	0.434	0.000	0.220	1.530	0.686	1.323	0.616	
Residual	15.128		0.000		0.702		0.826		
Variance Explained by the Model	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	
	0.130	0.508	0.034	0.247	0.323	0.787	0.133	0.667	

Sample Size	n		n		n		n	
Specimens	42		43		42		41	
Observations	169		172		187		145	
Model Comparison (LRT)	Model Deviance	LogL P						
Naze Single-Slope Model	993.82		-1119.75		606.34		474.93	
Naze Threshold Model	993.01	0.369	-1121.59	0.175	557.75	<0.001	455.88	<0.001

Supplementary Table 4. Linear Mixed Model (LMM) results contrasting the results of the single-slope model (“Naze Single-Slope Model”) and threshold model (“Naze Threshold Model”) for specimens from The Naze, and for response variables representing rib morphology (Z, RibsIn) or rib counts (OR, IR; see “Scaling Relationships for Naze Specimens” in the main text; see main text Fig. 3 for variable abbreviations). Only the explanatory variable (WH) was log-transformed before analysis; response variables were not log-transformed. For the Naze Threshold Model, fixed effect coefficient “WH (slope after threshold)*” is not a direct output of the model, but is calculated using model coefficients. Repeatability (Rep.) quantifies the proportion of the total variance (after removing the variance explained by the fixed effects) attributed to specimen identity (a unique identifier for each specimen). Marginal R^2 values (R^2_m) report the proportion of variance in the response variable explained by a model’s fixed effects (here, WH) and conditional R^2 values (R^2_c) report the proportion of variation in the response variable explained by both the fixed (WH) and random effects (specimen identity). “Model Comparison” section reports results of a likelihood ratio test comparing the performance of both LMMs, including deviance for each model and associated p-value (P) for the chi-squared statistic. For each variable, the results of the best-performing model are in bold, with green table headings. Confidence intervals for the position of the threshold were not able to be estimated in cases where they exceeded the boundaries of the range of possible threshold values tested (see Supplement Text section “Naze Scaling Relationships” for further detail).

		WWI		WRER		Z		Ribsins	
Size LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P
	Intercept	0.092 [0.062, 0.124]	<0.001	0.218 [0.183, 0.254]	<0.001	-2.073 [-5.605, 1.531]	0.241	1.008 [1.001, 1.014]	<0.001
	Whorl Height (WH)	-0.090 [-0.115, -0.065]	<0.001	0.092 [0.064, 0.121]	<0.001	4.231 [1.314, 7.115]	0.004	0.004 [-0.001, 0.010]	0.114
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.002	0.706	0.000	0.254	11.797	0.431	0.000	0.326
	Residual	0.001		0.001		15.545		0.000	
Variance Explained by the Model	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	
		0.142	0.748	0.200	0.403	0.034	0.451	0.010	0.333
Location LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P
	Intercept	0.068 [0.012, 0.128]	0.025	0.197 [0.149, 0.248]	<0.001	0.293 [-6.337, 6.089]	0.922	1.016 [1.006, 1.026]	<0.001
	Whorl Height (WH)	-0.097 [-0.123, -0.071]	<0.001	0.104 [0.074, 0.134]	<0.001	5.675 [2.952, 8.315]	<0.001	0.004 [-0.000, 0.010]	0.104
	Location								
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.002	0.690	0.000	0.256	6.998	0.312	0.000	0.226
Residual	0.001		0.001		15.464		0.000		
Variance Explained by the Model	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	R ² _m	R ² _c	
		0.199	0.752	0.239	0.434	0.208	0.455	0.161	0.350
Sample Size	n		n		n		n		
Specimens	98		89		106		111		
Observations	303		228		389		400		
Model Comparison (LRT)	Model Deviance	LogL P	Model Deviance	LogL P	Model Deviance	LogL P	Model Deviance	LogL P	
Size LMM	-1056.69		-796.40		2305.21		-2611.12		
Location LMM	-1071.67	0.020	-805.81	0.152	2261.09	<0.001	-2653.53	<0.001	

Supplementary Table 5. Linear Mixed Model (LMM) results contrasting the results of the Size LMM (incorporating whorl height as the only independent variable) and the Location LMM (additionally incorporating location as a multi-level factor fixed effect) for response variables best fit by a single-slope scaling relationship (see Supplementary Tables 1–2; see main text section “Location Effects on Morphology”). In all models, whorl height (WH) was log-transformed before analysis; response variables representing measures of conch morphology (WWI, WRER) were also log-transformed before analysis (see main text Fig. 3 for variable abbreviations). Fixed effects coefficients for locations are not shown in this table (see main text Fig. 6). Repeatability (Rep.) quantifies the proportion of the total variance (after removing the variance explained by the fixed effects) attributed to specimen identity (a unique identifier for each specimen). Marginal R² values (R²_m) report the proportion of variance in the response variable explained by a model’s fixed effects (here, WH) and conditional R² values (R²_c) report the proportion of variation in the response variable explained by both the fixed (WH) and random effects (specimen identity). “Model Comparison” section reports results of a likelihood ratio test comparing the performance of both LMMs, including deviance for each model and associated p-value (P) for the chi-squared statistic. For each variable, the results of the best-performing model are in bold, with green table headings.

		UWI		RUWI		WHER		OR		IR	
Size LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P						
	Intercept	-0.397 [-0.438, -0.359]	<0.001	-0.463 [-0.511, -0.419]	<0.001	0.040 [-0.081, 0.158]	0.507	12.588 [10.560, 14.690]	<0.001	10.142 [7.907, 12.183]	<0.001
	WH (slope before threshold)	-0.047 [-0.078, -0.013]	0.004	0.033 [-0.014, 0.084]	0.195	0.270 [0.151, 0.391]	<0.001	-5.922 [-8.033, -3.837]	<0.001	-3.670 [-5.717, -1.448]	<0.001
	WH (slope after threshold)*	-0.175 [-0.225, -0.125]	<0.001	-0.117 [-0.138, -0.097]	<0.001	0.127 [0.063, 0.192]	<0.001	5.481 [4.504, 6.458]	<0.001	2.845 [1.771, 3.918]	<0.001
	Threshold (mm WH)	21	NA	9	NA	12	NA	11	NA	12	NA
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.002	0.931	0.002	0.758	0.001	0.311	1.552	0.675	0.984	0.555
	Residual	0.000		0.001		0.003		0.748		0.791	
Variance Explained by the Model	R ² _m	R ² _c									
	0.161	0.942	0.155	0.795	0.307	0.522	0.242	0.754	0.091	0.595	
Location LMM	Fixed Effects	Est. [95%CI]	P	Est. [95%CI]	P						
	Intercept	-0.411 [-0.464, -0.360]	<0.001	-0.479 [-0.536, -0.421]	<0.001	-0.075 [-0.194, 0.044]	0.216	13.026 [10.752, 15.436]	<0.001	10.405 [7.994, 12.755]	<0.001
	WH (slope before threshold)	-0.057 [-0.086, -0.027]	<0.001	0.020 [-0.027, 0.070]	0.406	0.333 [0.226, 0.444]	<0.001	-5.637 [-7.768, -3.572]	<0.001	-3.457 [-5.442, -1.207]	0.001
	WH (slope after threshold)*	-0.165 [-0.234, -0.096]	<0.001	-0.115 [-0.190, -0.040]	<0.001	0.145 [-0.038, 0.328]	<0.001	5.646 [2.230, 9.062]	<0.001	3.109 [-0.272, 6.490]	<0.001
	Threshold (mm WH)	21	NA	9	NA	12	NA	11	NA	12	NA
	Location										
	Random Effects	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.	Variance	Rep.
	Specimen ID	0.001	0.887	0.001	0.639	0.001	0.226	1.257	0.626	0.825	0.511
Residual	0.000		0.001		0.003		0.750		0.790		
Variance Explained by the Model	R ² _m	R ² _c									
	0.476	0.941	0.421	0.791	0.437	0.564	0.359	0.760	0.204	0.610	
Sample Size	n		n		n		n		n		
Specimens	94		112		91		113		107		
Observations	259		665		237		438		358		
Model Comparison (LRT)	Model Deviance	LogL P									
Size LMM	-1220.14		-2676.34		-665.13		1351.12		1097.59		
Location LMM	-1274.16	<0.001	-2742.29	<0.001	-706.82	<0.001	1325.30	<0.001	1076.61	0.002	

Supplementary Table 6. Linear Mixed Model (LMM) results contrasting the results of the Size LMM (incorporating whorl height as the only independent variable) and the Location LMM (additionally incorporating location as a multi-level factor fixed effect) for response variables best fit by a threshold scaling relationship (see Supplementary Tables 1–2; see main text section “Location Effects on Morphology”). In all models, whorl height (WH) was log-transformed before analysis; response variables representing measures of conch morphology (UWI, RUWI, and WHER) were also log-transformed before analysis (see main text Fig. 3 for variable abbreviations). Fixed effect coefficients “WH (slope after threshold)*” are not direct outputs of the model, but are calculated using model coefficients. Fixed effects coefficients for locations are not shown in this table (see main text Fig. 6). Repeatability (Rep.) quantifies the proportion of the total variance (after removing the variance explained by the fixed effects) attributed to specimen identity (a unique identifier for each specimen). Marginal R² values (R²_m) report the proportion of variance in the response variable explained by a model’s fixed effects (here,

WH) and conditional R^2 values (R^2_c) report the proportion of variation in the response variable explained by both the fixed (WH) and random effects (specimen identity). “Model Comparison” section reports results of a likelihood ratio test comparing the performance of both LMMs, including deviance for each model and associated p-value (P) for the chi-squared statistic. For each variable, the results of the best-performing model are in bold, with green table headings.

	WWI		UWI		RUWI		WHER	
	AIC	Δ AIC	AIC	Δ AIC	AIC	Δ AIC	AIC	Δ AIC
Location LMM	-1051.7	21.7	-1252.2	0.8	-2720.3	56.6	-684.8	0
GAMM	-1073.4	0	-1253.0	0	-2776.9	0	-666.4	18.5

	Z		Ribsin		OR		IR	
	AIC	Δ AIC	AIC	Δ AIC	AIC	Δ AIC	AIC	Δ AIC
Location LMM	2281.1	7.2	-2633.5	0	1347.3	0	1098.6	0
GAMM	2273.9	0	-2620.9	12.7	1350.7	3.4	1100.3	1.7

Supplementary Table 7. Model performance comparison of the Location LMMs and GAMMs for all response variables best fit by the Location LMM (versus the Size LMM; see Supplementary Tables 5–6; see main text section “Interactive Effects of Size and Location”). Marginal Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) values are listed in bold for response variables for which the GAMM outperformed the Location LMM with a Δ AIC > 3 (see supplement text section “AIC for Comparison of LMMs and GAMMs” for more information). See main text Fig. 3 for variable abbreviations.

Gunnarites Taxon	Description/Diagnosis of Spath (1953)	Description/Diagnosis of Howarth (1966)
<i>G. antarcticus</i> (Weller, 1903)	Coarser ribbing than <i>G. bhavaniformis</i>	More evolute, less compressed, and with coarser ribs than <i>G. bhavaniformis</i>
<i>G. antarcticus</i> var. <i>inflata</i> (Kilian and Reboul, 1909)	More flexuous ribbing and greater whorl-thickness than <i>G. antarcticus</i>	
<i>G. bhavaniformis</i> (Kilian and Reboul, 1909)	Flat whorl-sides; Finer, more graceful ribbing, and more ribs per tubercle than <i>G. antarcticus</i> ; Ontogenetic transition from fine to coarse to fine ornamentation (in contrast with <i>G. gunnari</i>)	More involute, more compressed, and with finer ribs than <i>G. antarcticus</i> ; Intermediate between <i>G. antarcticus</i> and <i>G. kalika</i>
<i>G. bhavaniformis</i> var. <i>vegaensis</i> Spath, 1953	More compressed than <i>G. antarcticus</i> ; More sigmoidal ribbing than <i>G. bhavaniformis</i> ; Flexiradiate costation distinct at an early ontogenetic stage (in contrast with <i>G. antarcticus</i>)	
<i>G. flexuosus</i> Spath, 1953	Relatively fine, flexiradiate and highly crenulate ribbing occurs from an early ontogenetic stage; Less conspicuous constrictions compared to <i>G. antarcticus</i> ; Inner whorls more finely ribbed than <i>G. pachys</i>	
<i>G. flexuosus</i> var. <i>transitoria</i> Spath, 1953	More rounded whorl-sides and ribbing tends to become stronger and more widely spaced than in <i>G. flexuosus</i>	
<i>G. gunnari</i> (Kilian and Reboul, 1909)	More compressed than <i>G. antarcticus</i> or <i>G. bhavaniformis</i> ; Ribbing becomes increasingly more widely spaced (in contrast with <i>G. bhavaniformis</i>)	
<i>G. kalika</i> (Stoliczka, 1895)	Finer and more sigmoidal ribbing than <i>G. bhavaniformis</i>	More involute, more compressed, and with finer ribs than <i>G. bhavaniformis</i>

<i>G. kalika</i> var. <i>gracilis</i> Spath, 1953	In early ontogeny, ribs are flexuous and finely striate, but in later ontogeny, ribs are more coarsely crenulate	
<i>G. kalika</i> var. <i>nana</i> Spath, 1953	Develops a body chamber at a smaller diameter than <i>G. kalika</i>	
<i>G. pachys</i> Spath, 1953	More graceful and flexiradiate ribbing than <i>G. antarcticus</i> and <i>G. antarcticus</i> var. <i>inflata</i> ; More rapid increase in whorl thickness than other <i>Gunnarites</i> species	Wider and more robust whorls than <i>G. antarcticus</i> , but with flexuous ribbing comparable to <i>G. antarcticus</i>
<i>G. pachys</i> var. <i>media</i> Spath, 1953	More compressed and less closely ribbed than <i>G. pachys</i>	

Supplementary Table 8. Summaries the typological approaches of Spath (1953) and Howarth (1966) to *Gunnarites* in the James Ross Basin. Descriptions of diagnostic characteristics are listed for each taxon, but these are not necessarily comprehensive taxon descriptions and the reader is referred to the original publications for more detail.

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Results of the linear mixed models (LMMs) depicting the scaling relationship between conch morphology response variables and whorl height (WH) on a log-log scale, for specimens from The Naze (see main text sections “Scaling Relationships for Naze Specimens” and “Scaling Relationships of Morphological Variables for Naze Specimens”). See main text Fig. 3 for variable abbreviations. Black lines show the predicted scaling relationship of the best-fitting LMM for each response variable (either a single-slope or threshold relationship); grey envelopes depict the 95% confidence interval. For threshold relationships, a grey vertical line indicates the position of the threshold, and dotted lines indicate the associated 95% confidence interval. Points show raw data. All plots drawn with 1:1 aspect ratio.

Supplementary Figure 2. Results of the linear mixed models (LMMs) depicting the scaling relationship between ornament count (OR, IR) or ornament morphology (Z, Ribsin) response variables and log-transformed whorl height (WH), for specimens from The Naze (see main text sections “Scaling Relationships for Naze Specimens” and “Scaling Relationships of Morphological Variables for Naze Specimens”). See main text Fig. 3 for variable abbreviations. Black lines show the predicted scaling relationship of the best-fitting LMM for each response variable (either a single-slope or threshold relationship); grey envelopes depict the 95% confidence interval. For threshold relationships, a grey vertical line indicates the position of the threshold, and dotted lines indicate the associated 95% confidence interval. Points show raw data. Due to differing magnitudes of values on different axes, plots are drawn with arbitrary aspect ratios for ease of visualization.

Supplementary Figure 3. Spearman rank correlation matrix for all morphometric variables. Conch variables were log-transformed before analysis; ornament variables were not log-transformed. See main text Fig. 3 for variable abbreviations. Colored squares indicate significant ($p < 0.05$) relationships between pairs of variables. For significant relationships, Spearman’s rho value is listed, with box color corresponding to strength and direction of the relationship. See supplement text section “Correlations Between Variables” for more information.

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